

An open-source tool for water, energy and waste management integrated assessment

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1. Introduction – Water and energy integration systems (WEIS) in process industry plants consists in the exploitation of possible interdependencies between partial or full existing industrial processes. The WEIS overall aim is to promote energy efficiency, water efficiency and pollutant emission mitigation simultaneously through waste heat recovery (WHR), thermal energy storage (TES) and heat-driven wastewater treatment [1–3]. This work introduces an innovative simulation and optimisation tool for water, energy and waste management strategies assessment in industrial processes. This tool is primarily developed in Modelica language also adapting a part of ThermoPower library [4]. It is divided in the following modules:

- Heat recovery module (including combustion-based processes of industrial processes industry and WRH technologies);
- Thermal energy storage (sensible and latent TES units);
- Water treatment (water-using processes and heat-driven wastewater treatment units) and;
- Wastewater-to-energy (sustainable fuel production technologies from wastewater).

2. Experimental – This work aims to assess the viability of a WEIS within a process industry plant (namely a sanitaryware production plant), focusing in direct hot air recovery at two thermal processes (natural gas savings), a heat exchanger network for the heating of two water streams (hot utility savings, which in this case is natural gas) and a multi-effect distillation unit to for treated water recycling (water savings). The tool enables the assembling of each component model and perform the energy and economic assessment.

3. Results and Discussion – The economic viability assessment is presented in Table I.

Table I. Determination of economic viability of WEIS

Natural Gas (Thermal Processes)				
Process	Initial Case (kg/h)	Improved Case (kg/h)	Energy Savings (GJ/h)	Savings (k€/year)
Kiln 1	196.50	163.34	1.50	98.14
Kiln 2	103.50	81.36	1.00	65.51
Hot Utility				
Stream	Hot Utility Savings (MJ/h)		Savings (k€/year)	
Water Stream 1	168.11		11.01	
Water Stream 2	126.98		8.32	
Water Utility				
Initial Case (kg/h)	Improved Case (kg/h)	MED CAPEX (k€)	MED OPEX (k€/year)	Savings (k€/year)
913.04	113.04	46.02	6.01	7.62
Total				
Total Savings (k€/year)		Investment Cost (k€)		Payback Period (years)
110.95		155.36		1.4

4. Conclusions – This work shows the functionality of an innovative computational tool for the conceptualization of water and energy systems to be installed in process industry plants aiming to optimise the energy and water efficiency as well as waste mitigation. The energy and economic assessment show significant natural gas savings, hot utility savings and water savings with a very attractive payback time of 1.4 years. The proposed tool may be further developed to conceptualize systems in other real-scale plants.

5. References

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